

Whole-genome sequencing of *Bacillus velezensis* strain B15 isolated from *Fagonia glutinosa* growing in the arid region of Tunisia

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Abstract

This study reports the complete genome sequence (CGS) of *Bacillus velezensis* B15 isolated from the roots of *Fagonia glutinosa*, which was sampled from the arid region of Tunisia. CGS will provide valuable insights into implications of genes involved in plant growth promotion and biocontrol, which is a crucial step to its further use as a biostimulant agent.

Introduction

Plant-beneficial microorganisms linked to increased plant health and productivity are emerging as alternatives to agrochemical-based approaches. *Bacillus*-based agro-alternatives are gaining attention owing to their spore-forming ability that can resist harsh environmental conditions for an extended period of time (Radhakrishnan et al., 2017). Thus, the search for well-adapted bacteria co-existing with native plants growing in extreme environments should be worthwhile.

The genus *Fagonia* is a desert shrub that is characterized by its high adaptations to climatic conditions. *Fagonia* spp. are confined to warm and arid areas in which they form an important part of the vegetation (Beier, 2005). There is scarce information in the literature reporting the microbiome co-existing with *Fagonia* genus. Only one study reported the isolation of *Bacillus* and *Paenibacillus* species from *F. mollis* (Alkahtani et al., 2020).

In this study, we report the whole genome sequence data of the bacterium *Bacillus velezensis* strain B15 isolated from *F. glutinosa*.

Material and Methods

Collection of plant material

The bacterium was isolated from the roots of the wild plant *F. glutinosa*, collected from the arid region of Tunisia (Bou ghrara, Mednine, 33°31'58.0"N, 10°40'20.2"E). The soil is characterized as an arid, native saline soil (Omar et al., 2020). Samples were placed in clean plastic bags, brought to the laboratory, and used for further experimental purposes.

Isolation and purification of bacterial endophytes

Roots were surface-sterilized by a stepwise washing procedure through the following protocol: 70% alcohol for 1 min, sodium hypochlorite (2,5% Cl) for 4 min, ethanol for 30 s, and 3 rinses in sterile distilled water, according to Costa et al. (2012). Afterwards, surface-sterilised leaves were macerated in buffer solution (0,9% NaCl) using a sterile mortar and pestle. Serial tenfold dilutions of the tissue extract were prepared in sterilized distilled water. From each dilution, 100 µl were spread on 10% tryptic soy agar (TSA)

plates and incubated at 28 °C. Emerging bacterial colonies were purified through repetitive single-colony isolation.

Whole-genome sequencing of bacteria

The DNA extraction of B15, the Illumina genome sequencing, and assembly were conducted by the sequencing service provider microbesNG (The BioHub Birmingham, UK) according to their protocols accessible at <https://microbesng.com/>. Briefly, genomic DNA was subjected to whole-genome sequencing on an Illumina NovaSeq 6000 (Illumina, San Diego, USA) using a 250 bp paired end protocol. Reads were trimmed using Trimmomatic version 0.3 and then were de novo assembled into contigs using SPAdes version 3.7. The complete genome sequence of B15 was annotated using Prokka version 1.11. The preliminary taxonomic classification of the genome sequence was performed using Kraken. Prediction of protein coding features and tRNA was performed utilizing Prodigal version 2.6, while rRNA prediction was carried out using ARAGORN version 1.2.

Precise species identification and phylogenetic analysis

To confirm the taxonomic assignment generated from Kraken, the core genes *rpoB*, *pycA*, and *aroE* were used for the identification of the B15 strain. The sequences of the core genes were extracted from the assembled genome of the B15 strain by using the Standalone BLAST program. These sequences were further aligned and compared with the sequences of *Bacillus* species by using the NCBI Basic Local Alignment Search Tools, nucleotide (BLASTn) program available at NCBI (<http://www.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov>). Alignments of the sequences with the highest homologous hits mined from BLASTn and the gene sequences extracted from the assembled genome were performed using the MUSCLE program in MEGA version 11. Afterwards, a phylogenetic tree was constructed using the maximum likelihood method with 100 bootstrap replicates in MEGA. The phylogenetic tree was visualized with iTOL version 6.

Results

Genomic features

The assembly of the sequence reads resulted in 10 contigs (≥ 1000 bp), with the largest contig measuring 2,101,272 bp. The cumulative contig length of the genome assembly accounted for 3,993,252 bp with up to 112,6 X mean coverage. The genomic GC content is determined to be 46,4%. The other genome features are listed in Table 1.

Table 1. Summary statistics for the *Bacillus velezensis* B15 genome

Biosample	<u>SAMN38053693</u>	Mean coverage	112,6
# contigs (≥ 1000 bp)	10	CDS	4,079,0
Largest contig	2,101,272	tRNA	84
Total length	3,993,252	tmRNA	1
GC (%)	46,4	Gene bank accession (assembly)	<u>JAZBQT000000000</u>
N50	2,101,272	Gene bank accession (reads)	<u>SRR26629869</u>

Phylogenetic analysis

The phylogenetic trees constructed from *rpoB* and *pycA* genes (Figure 1A and 1B) showed that B15 branched with *B. velezensis* and *B. amyloliquefaciens* which make them not sufficient markers for the differentiation of these closely related *Bacillus* species. The phylogenetic analyses of *aroE* gene sequences (Figure 1C) displayed high specificity for *B. velezensis*.

Fig 1. Phylogenetic trees of *Bacillus velezensis* B15. The phylogenetic trees are based on *rpoB* (A), *pycA* (B), and *aroE* (C) gene alignments obtained by MEGA 11 software using the maximum likelihood method.

Data availability

This whole-genome shotgun has been deposited at DDBJ/ENA/GenBank under the accession number [JAZBQT000000000](https://www.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/nuclseq/JAZBQT000000000). Raw sequence reads have been deposited in the NCBI Sequence Read Archive under the BioProject number PRJNA1011052 and run numbers [SRR26629869](https://www.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/sra/SRR26629869).

Statement on continuing work

The datasets are being shared prior to formal publication and should be regarded as preliminary.

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